

Appendices to Should We Fight Poverty or Reduce Its Harm? How the Language of Moral Foundations Theory Affect Donations to Poverty-Relief Charities.

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Appendix A. Not for publication.

Instructions' and materials used in the experiment.

The following instructions were printed and given to participants. These instructions were also read aloud:

This survey has 3 separate parts.

1. Part 1 is a survey on inflation, wealth, and your opinions on various topics. When you complete part 1, place part 1 face down in the bin at the front of the room labeled "Part 1"

Please notice that part 1.b. refers to a set of graphs that have been printed separately.

After you turn in part 1, you can start part 2. If anyone would like assistance turning in the survey, raise your hand when you finish and one of us will come to you.

2. Please read the instructions to part 2 carefully, because this is the receipt that will determine your earnings for today. When you finish part 2, place that sheet of paper face down in the bin at the front of the room labeled "Part 2".

After you turn in part 2, you can start part 3.

3. It will take us a few minutes to prepare your earnings. Please complete the final demographic survey while you wait. Once you finish this survey, place it face down in the bin labeled "Part 3".

Bring your ID number with to collect your earnings. Give your ID number to the person at the computer terminal so you can collect the correct amount in cash. You are free to leave after receiving your earnings.

If there is a line, please allow space for distancing. We want all earnings to be private.

You are welcome to stay and witness any donations to charity. Otherwise, you are free to leave.

Thank you for participating in today's survey!

Parts 1a. and 1b. of the survey are on inflation and the distribution of income. These materials are included in our companion paper.

Part 1c. of the survey is the MFQ30 Questionnaire. Original version is posted here:

<https://moralfoundations.org/questionnaires/>

Our version changes the formatting, and is available upon request.

Part 1c: Your opinions.

When you decide whether something is right or wrong, to what extent are the following considerations relevant to your thinking? Please rate each statement using this scale:

(circle one number for each factor):

Whether or not someone...	not relevant at all	not very relevant	slightly relevant	somewhat relevant	very relevant	extremely relevant
suffered emotionally	0	1	2	3	4	5
was treated differently than others	0	1	2	3	4	5
showed love for their country	0	1	2	3	4	5
showed a lack of respect for authority	0	1	2	3	4	5
violated standards of purity and decency	0	1	2	3	4	5
was good at math	0	1	2	3	4	5
cared for the weak or vulnerable	0	1	2	3	4	5
acted unfairly	0	1	2	3	4	5
did something to betray their group	0	1	2	3	4	5
conformed to the traditions of society	0	1	2	3	4	5
did something disgusting	0	1	2	3	4	5
was cruel	0	1	2	3	4	5
was denied their rights	0	1	2	3	4	5
showed a lack of loyalty	0	1	2	3	4	5
caused chaos or disorder	0	1	2	3	4	5
acted in a way that God would approve	0	1	2	3	4	5

Please read the following sentences and indicate your agreement or disagreement:

	Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree
Compassion for those who are suffering is the most crucial virtue.	0	1	2	3	4	5
When the government makes laws, the number one principle should be ensuring that everyone is treated fairly.	0	1	2	3	4	5
I am proud of my country's history.	0	1	2	3	4	5
Respect for authority is something all children need to learn.	0	1	2	3	4	5
People should not do things that are disgusting, even if no one is harmed.	0	1	2	3	4	5
It is better to do good than to do bad.	0	1	2	3	4	5
One of the worst things a person could do is hurt a defenseless animal.	0	1	2	3	4	5
Justice is the most important requirement for a society.	0	1	2	3	4	5
People should be loyal to their family members, even when they have done something wrong.	0	1	2	3	4	5
Men and women each have different roles to play in society.	0	1	2	3	4	5
I would call some acts wrong on the grounds that they are unnatural.	0	1	2	3	4	5

	Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree
It can never be right to kill a human being.	0	1	2	3	4	5
I think it's morally wrong that rich children inherit a lot of money while poor children inherit nothing.	0	1	2	3	4	5
It is more important to be a team player than to express oneself.	0	1	2	3	4	5
If I were a soldier and disagreed with my commanding officer's orders, I would obey anyway because that is my duty.	0	1	2	3	4	5
Chastity is an important and valuable virtue.	0	1	2	3	4	5

This section of the survey concludes with questions related to TANF. Those materials are included with the companion paper.

Part 2 is the earnings receipt. The treatment is indicated in parentheses in this appendix. These labels were not included in the experimental materials used (next page).

Part 2. Your Earnings (individualizing treatment)

ID Number: _____

Thank you for participating in the survey of the economy. The information you have provided may be of interest to educators and policy makers to better understand the economy, wealth, and poverty.

The researchers of this study have partnered with the following organizations in their work reducing poverty. These organizations were selected because of their reputation for compassion and proven record of reducing the harm done to vulnerable populations affected by poverty. Donations help reduce suffering of the poor and help them have opportunities in life. If you wish to show kindness by donating any of your \$15 earnings to any organization or organizations, please write the amount (whole dollar amounts only please) in the space next to the organization. Of course, you have the option to not donate at this time.

	<p>Feeding America Feeding America’s mission is to provide care by feeding America's hungry through a nationwide network of member food banks and engage our country to reduce the harms caused by hunger. Feeding America distributes food and grocery products through a nationwide certified member network and advocates for public policies that benefit America's hungry.</p>
	<p>Feed The Children One of America’s most compassionate charities providing food, clothing, medical care, education, and emergency relief to children in the United States since 1979. Feed The Children supplies backpacks filled with ready-to-eat meals, toothbrushes, school supplies and age appropriate books to homeless students enrolled in public schools.</p>
	<p>Goodwill Industries of Mississippi Goodwill works to enhance the dignity and quality of life of individuals and families by strengthening communities, eliminating barriers to opportunity, and helping people in need reach their full potential through learning and the power of work.</p>
	<p>United Way of Northeast Mississippi One of the goals of the United Way is to help families achieve financial safety. United Way brings people together to build equitable communities where everyone can thrive</p>

_____ Total amount donated.

_____ Your Earnings.

If you do not wish to donate to these charities at this time, simply check here: _____

(These two numbers need to sum to \$15)

Part 2. Your Earnings (binding treatment)

ID Number: _____

Thank you for participating in the survey of the economy. The information you have provided may be of interest to educators and policy makers to better understand the economy, wealth, and poverty.

The researchers of this study have partnered with the following organizations in their work fighting poverty. These organizations were selected because of their reputation for promoting individual responsibility and proven record of fighting poverty. Many religious and political leaders ask citizens to donate to worthy causes. If you want to take pride in the civic duty of donating any of your \$15 earnings to any organization or organizations, please write the amount (whole dollar amounts only please) in the space next to the organization. Of course, you have the option to not donate at this time.

	<p>Feeding America Feeding America’s mission is to feed America's hungry through a nationwide network of member food banks and engage our country in the fight to end hunger. Feeding America distributes food and grocery products through a nationwide certified member network and advocates for public policies that benefit America's hungry.</p>
	<p>Feed The Children One of America’s most effective charities providing food, clothing, medical care, education, and emergency relief to children in the United States since 1979. Feed The Children supplies backpacks filled with ready-to-eat meals, toothbrushes, school supplies and age appropriate books to homeless students enrolled in public schools.</p>
	<p>Goodwill Industries of Mississippi Goodwill works to enhance the integrity and dignity of individuals and families by strengthening communities, eliminating barriers to opportunity, and helping people in need reach their full potential through learning and the power of work.</p>
	<p>United Way of Northeast Mississippi One of the goals of the United Way is to help people on the road to economic independence. United Way brings individuals together to build a strong nation where everyone can thrive.</p>

_____ Total amount donated.

_____ Your Earnings.

If you do not wish to donate to these charities at this time, simply check here: _____

(These two numbers need to sum to \$15)

Part 3. Demographic Survey

ID Number: _____

1. AGE _____

2. What is your gender identity? Female Male Other (please specify) _____ Prefer not to disclose

3. Do you regularly attend religious services? (circle one): NO YES

4. Which of the following categories best describes you? (Circle one number. If more than one applies, which do you primarily identify with?)

01 African, African-American, or Black

02 Asian or Asian/American (including South Asian and Indian)

03 Hawaiian or Pacific Islander

04 Hispanic-Black/Spanish-speaking Black

05 Hispanic-White/Spanish-speaking White

06 Middle Eastern or North African

07 Native American/American Indian or Alaska Native

08 White/Caucasian

09 Other (Please specify: _____)

5. Class (Circle one)

Freshman Sophomore Junior Senior Graduate Student

6. Major (Circle one)

Economics Other business Psychology Sciences Engineering Arts Other

7. How many Economics classes have you taken at the university level? (Circle one)

None One Two Three Four Five Six or more

8. How would you best describe your political affiliation (circle one number)

00 Strongly Democratic 01 Weakly Democratic 02 Independent

03 Weakly Republican 04 Strongly Republican 05 Other (Please Specify) _____

9. What is your GPA (circle one range)?

below 2.00 2 to 2.49 2.5 to 2.99 3 to 3.49 above 3.5

10. Do you think most things in life work out for people if they just keep trying? (Circle one alternative)

01 Yes 02 No

11. Do you think it is better to be smart than to be lucky? (Circle one alternative)

01 Smart 02 Lucky

12. If you were given the following two options, which would you most prefer? (Circle one option)

Option A: A 10% chance of winning \$20 and a 90% chance of winning \$16.

Option B: A 10% chance of winning \$38.50 and a 90% chance of winning \$1.

13. If you were given the following two options, which would you most prefer? (Circle one option)

Option C: A 90% chance of winning \$20 and a 10% chance of winning \$16.

Option D: A 90% chance of winning \$38.50 and a 10% chance of winning \$1.

14. If it takes 5 machines 5 minutes to make 5 widgets, how long would it take 100 machines to make 100 widgets? _____ minutes.

15. How many *letters* appear in the following string of characters?

8#h^56g8923458ft97jm34jKL#(u9j(#*mt92j2564j*V#

_____ letters.

When you have completed this final survey, you can bring it forward to receive your earnings. After you have received your earnings, your time in the survey has ended. Once all participants have completed their surveys, a researcher and the monitor will determine how much has been donated to charity, and will mail checks to the charities. All participants are welcome to stay if you wish to learn how much has been donated to charity, and to witness the payments to charity delivered to the post office on campus. Otherwise, you are free to leave. Please make sure you have all of your belongings with you as you exit.

Thank you for participating in today's survey!

Appendix B. Not for publication. Additional data analysis.

Table Appendix B1. OLS model results: donations to charity.

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Moral Foundations Appeal (binding treatment = 1)	-1.63 (0.99)	-1.81* (0.99)	-1.84* (0.97)
Progressivism Score		0.92 (0.62)	1.63** (0.68)
Female			-2.21** (0.99)
White			0.98 (1.28)
Regular Church Attendance			1.19 (1.14)
Constant	4.62	4.53	4.03
R ²	0.02	0.04	0.08
N	127	127	127

Notes: Robust standard errors in parentheses. *** 1%, ** 5%, * 10% level

Table Appendix B2. Tobit model: donations to charity. Upper limit only (upper limit = 15).

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Moral Foundations Appeal (binding treatment = 1)	-1.90 (1.18)	-2.10* (1.18)	-2.11* (1.14)
Progressivism Score		1.06 (0.74)	1.82** (0.80)
Female			-2.47** (1.18)
White			1.06 (1.50)
Regular Church Attendance			1.26 (1.33)
Constant	5.21	5.10	4.62
Pseudo R ²	0.00	0.01	0.01
Pseudo-likelihood	-376.30	-375.32	-372.91
N	127	127	127

Notes: Robust standard errors in parentheses. *** 1%, ** 5%, * 10% level

Table Appendix B3. Probit model results. Dependent variable: Give = 1 if positive amount donated; 0 otherwise.

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Moral Foundations Appeal (binding treatment = 1)	-0.34 (0.23)	-0.37 (0.23)	-0.42* (0.24)
Progressivism Score		0.11 (0.14)	0.39** (0.18)
Female = 1 0 otherwise			-0.66*** (0.24)
White = 1 0 otherwise			0.40 (0.31)
Regular Church Attendance = 1 0 otherwise			0.52* (0.29)
N	127	127	127

Notes: Robust standard errors in parentheses. *** 1%, ** 5%, * 10% level

Table Appendix B4.

	Mean Donation (observations)					
	Math ¹		Good over Bad ²		Counting Task ³	
	Pass	Fail	Pass	Fail	Pass	Fail
Individualizing Treatment (progressive language)	\$4.75 (n = 56)	\$3.57 (n = 7)	\$4.69 (n = 62)	\$0.00 (n = 1)	\$4.75 (n = 55)	\$3.75 (n = 8)
Binding Treatment (conservative language)	\$3.00 (n = 51)	\$2.92 (n = 13)	\$3.13 (n = 61)	\$0.00 (n = 3)	\$3.11 (n = 56)	\$2.13 (n = 8)

Notes: ¹ “When you decide whether something is right or wrong, to what extent are the following considerations relevant to your thinking? Whether or not someone was good at math.” Attention failures are defined as Likert scale ranking of 3 (somewhat relevant), 4, and 5 (extremely relevant).

² “Indicate your agreement or disagreement: It is better to do good than to do bad.” Attention failures are defined as a Likert scale ranking of 0 (strong disagree), 1, and 2 (slight disagree).

³ How many *letters* appear in the following string of characters?
 8#h^56g8923458ft97jm34jKL#(u9j(#*mt92j2564j*V#
 Attention failures are defined as any count other than 16.

We do not conduct statistical tests because the number of observations in many cells is low, but we note a general pattern: donations are higher in the individualizing treatments than the binding treatments. The one exception is among those who fail the “better to do good than bad” attention check. In that one case, the single participant in the individualizing treatment who failed donated \$0, and the three participants in the binding treatment who failed also donated \$0.

The total number of attention check fails equals 40. The number of observations dropped is 38, meaning 38 participants passed 2 of the 3 attention checks. Two participants failed two checks, but both of these counted 15 characters when the correct response is 16. Our interpretation of the attention checks is that participants appear to answer sincerely.